

Testing the Effect of Different Type of Diets on Cattle a Case Study of Department of Animal Production and Health Science Eksu.

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ABSTRACT

This research work was carried out to test the effect of different diets on cattle, in Department of Animal production and health Sciences, faculty of Agriculture, Ekiti State University Ado – Ekiti, Nigeria. In this study, the data used were divided into two feed consumption and milk production. The design used is Randomize complete block design (RCBD). We can see from the analysis that diets were significantly different for feed consumption and for milk production diets have no significant differences.

Key words: Diets, cattle, feed, consumption, experimental design, error

INTRODUCTION

Farm animal can in one hand be divided into non ruminants and ruminants, the latter comprising cattle, sheep, gazelles, giraffes, mose and antelope. Ruminant animals have four stomach – rumen, reticulum, omasum and abomasums. Cattle are ruminants meaning that they have a digestive system that allows use of otherwise indigestible foods by repeatedly regurgitating and re – chewing them as “cud”, and then the cud is then the cud is then re - swallowed and further digested by specialized microorganism in the rumen, cattle production has become commercialized into big business in many countries including Nigeria.

Cattle have been around for thousands of years. Cattle belong to the genus, modern breeds descended from two varieties of the species Taurus. These wild oxen called anchors had a hump over its shoulders. Braham cattle developed from this hampered variety. But most united state and united European breeds is descendant of humpies varieties. People have raised cattle, for thousands of year pictures carved in ancient Egyptian tombs show oxen pulling plows treading grain. Cattle raisers once followed their herds from land to land as the cattle searched for grass to eat. Later, some of these herders and their families settled in one place, they fed their cattle grain in addition to grass. The first cattle were used as work animal as well as for producing milk and beef. People began to breed cattle either as beef animal or for producing milk. Cattle dairy and beef comprises a major portion of animal agriculture. Traditionally, animals and dairy science have been divided into then discipline of physiology, nutrition and animal breeding. Increased production efficiency should result from the incorporation of present knowledge of behavior research. Cattle productions are farmed for beef, veal, dairy, leather and milk. Milk as exploit its relative abundance in essential amino acid, essential fatty acids iron and other nutrient required for growth

or healing and for children, lactation and for convalescence. Cattle are commonly used for conservation, grazing simple to maintain grass land for wild-life.

Cattle were first brought to the Americans by Norwaigian. Vikings in the early 1000’s. Railroads has helped cattle ranchers by transporting cattle to the eastern market railroads cars that were refrigerated made it possible to ship meat product long distances.

METHODOLOGY

Randomized complete block design (RCBD) is a design use when the experimental units are not homogeneous and thus can be allocated to groups of block such that the variation among blocks is maximized while the variation within any particular block is minimized. These blocks are sometimes called the replicates.

The model for randomized complete block design (RCBD) contained the assumption of no interaction effects, when both the block and treatment effect are fixed and there are b (block replication) and t(treatment).

There are two basic types of error that can be committed in the conduct of an experiment.

Type 1 error is the error committed when rejecting a true null hypothesis H₀. The probability of committed type 1 error is called the level of significance, it is the maximum probability allotted to committing type 1 error. It is usually denoted by α

Type 11 error this is when accepting a false null hypothesis. The probability of committing type 11 error is usually denoted by β

The probabilities of committing the two errors and also of making correct decision are presented below

DECISION	TRUE H ₀	FALSE H ₀
Accepted	1 – α	B
Rejected	A	1 – β

MODEL FOR RCBD

Y_{ij} = the observation i th treatment j th block

μ = the overall mean effect

T_i = the effect of i th treatment

B_j = The effect of j th block

E_{ij} = The random error in the i th and j th cell

For $i = 1, 2, \dots, t$

$J = 1, 2, \dots, b$

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE (ANOVA) TABLE

Sources of variation	Sum of Square	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F calculated
Block	SSB	$(b - 1)$	MSB	MSB/MSE
Treatment	SSt	$(t - 1)$	MSt	MSt/MSE
Error	SSE	$(b - 1)(t - 1)$	MSE	
Total	SST	$(bt - 1)$ or $(n - 1)$		

TEST STATISTIC

$F^* = MSB/MSE$

$F^* = MSt/MSE$

Reject the null hypothesis if F calculated $>$ F tabulated and there exist a level of significant and Accept the null hypothesis if F calculated is $<$ F tabulated and there exist no level of significant.

DATA ANALYSIS

Feed consumption was taken into consideration. Diets are taken as treatment and days are taken as blocks, then the data on Average milk production was analyzed.

DATA ON FEED CONSUMPTION

TREATMENT

Block	W7.0	W9.0	W4.5	W0.0	TOTAL
Day 1	63.86	45.38	48.97	52.29	210.5
Day 2	59.50	42.78	46.75	49.77	198.8
Day 3	54.10	40.27	45.72	45.20	185.29
Day 4	50.05	44.10	42.81	41.70	178.66
Day 5	48.79	46.25	39.75	41.10	175.89
Day 6	43.20	39.85	40.56	42.30	165.91
Day 7	45.80	41.60	43.29	43.25	173.97

COMPUTATION OF SUM OF SQUARES

Correction factor = $\frac{Y..^2}{n}$

$$c.f = \frac{(63.86+59.50+54.10+\dots+43.25)^2}{28}$$

$$= \frac{1661495.22}{28}$$

$$= 59339.115$$

SUM OF SQUARE FOR TREATMENT (SSt) = $\sum Y_{.i}^2/b - c.f$

$$SSt = \frac{(365.30)^2 + (300.23)^2 + (307)^2 + (315.61)^2}{7} - 59339.115$$

$$= \frac{59709.0625}{7} - 59339.115$$

$$= 369.94$$

SUM OF SQUARE FOR BLOCK (SSB) = $\sum Y_{.j}^2/t - c.f$

$$SSB = \frac{(210.5)^2 + (198.8)^2 + \dots + (173.94)^2}{4} - 59339.115$$

$$= \frac{238802.0135}{4} - 59339.115$$

$$= 361.38$$

SUM OF SQUARE FOR TOTAL (SST) = $\sum(Y_{ij})^2 - C.F$

$$SST = (63.86)^2 + (59.50)^2 + \dots + (48.79)^2 - (59339.115)$$

$$= 60256.2345 - 59339.115$$

$$= 917.119$$

SUM OF SQUARE FOR ERROR (SSE)

$$SSE = SST - SSB - SSt$$

$$= 917.119 - 361.38 - 369.94$$

$$= 185.799$$

COMPUTATION OF MEAN SQUARE

Degree of freedom for block (dfb)

$$Dfb = (b - 1) = (7 - 1)$$

Degree of freedom for treatment (dft)

$$Dft = (t - 1) = (4 - 1)$$

Degree of freedom for error (dfe) = $(b - 1)(t - 1)$

$$Dfe = (7-1)(4-1) = 6 \times 3 = 18$$

Degree of freedom for Total (dft) = $(bt - 1)$ or $(n - 1)$

$$(7 \times 4) - 1 = 27$$

MEAN SQUARE FOR BLOCK (MSB)

$$MSB = SSB/dfb$$

$$361.35/6 = 60.225$$

MEAN SQUARE FOR TREATMENT (MSt)

$$MSt = SSt/dft = 369.9126/2$$

MEAN SQUARE FOR ERROR (MSE)

$$MSE = SSE/dfe = 185.820/18$$

COMPUTATION OF F - CALCULATED

FOR BLOCK

$$= MSB/MSE = 60.225/10.323 = 5.83$$

FOR TREATMENT

$$MSt/MSE = 123.30/10.32 = 11.94$$

F - TABULATED

For Treatment at 5% level of significant

$$F_{0.05} (3, 18) = 3.16$$

For Treatment at 1% level of significant

$$F_{0.01} (3, 18) = 5.09$$

For Block at 5% level of significant

$$F_{0.05} (6, 18) = 2.66$$

For Block at 1% level of significant

$$F_{0.01} (6, 18) = 4.01$$

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE (ANOVA) TABLE FOR FEED CONSUMPTION

ANOVA TABLE

Sources of Variation	Sum of Square	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F - Calculated	F – Tabulated	
					5%	1%
Block	361.35	6	60.22	5.83	2.66	4.01
Treatment	369.91	3	123.30	11.94	3.16	5.09
Error	185.85	18	10.32			
Total	917.08	27				

FREIDMAN TEST STATISTIC

$$\chi^2 F = SSt + (SSt + SSE)/b(t - 1)$$

$$\chi^2 F = 369.91 + (369.91 + 185.82)/7 \times 3$$

$$\chi^2 F = 369.91 + 555.73/21$$

$$\chi^2 F = 369.91 + 26.46 = 396.37$$

$$\chi^2 F = 396.3$$

$$\chi^2(b - 1),_{0.05}$$

$$\chi^2_{6,(0.05)} = 14.04$$

$\chi^2 F > \chi^2_{6,(0.05)}$, then we reject the null hypothesis H0 that is diets were significantly different.

Summary

This research work was carried out to test the effect of different diets on cattle in Department of Animal Production and health Science, faculty of agriculture, University of Ado – Ekiti, Nigeria. Data were analyzed using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Freidman’s test Statistic, from the result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA), Freidman’s test, for feed consumption, the F – calculated is greater than F – tabulated, hence we rejected the null hypothesis H0 that is diets were significantly different.

CONCLUSION

The result of analysis on effect of diets on cattle for feed consumption, diets were significantly different. We hereby concluded that diets have greater effects on cattle milk production.

Recommendation

Since Diets has greater effect on cattle production, we hereby recommended that farm Animal production should cultivate the habit of feeding their cattle with good diets such as, steam – flaked corn, cotton seed meal, fat (yellow greases) and molasses. For increment in their milk production.

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